

Editorial Note

Sharing Experiences and Possibilities for Design Research

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I must address to all readers of International Journal of Design and Allied Sciences (IJDas) for their interest in Design Research. I have spent about three decades of my career in a renowned R&D organization in India researching the design and development of hardware and software of national importance. The journey and experiences were amazing. My initial experience while sitting inside an armored vehicle was to discover that the commandant rests his feet on the gunner's head, who is seated a level below! No consideration was given to the human component for whom the vehicle was designed, but a hundred percent output was expected of the machine. The same story has continued in different forms even today but to a lesser extent. Shall we consider it as a lack of knowledge or the developer's lack of awareness regarding the users' capabilities and limitations? (Chávez & Colin, 2016; Khadilkar & Mani, 2013; Treu & Treu 1994; van Velsen et al., 2022).

My repeated persuasions mostly failed because of the age-old traditional concept that humans can adjust and endure anything in any environment. If a person can enter through a 'rat hole' and rescue the trapped miners, then why can humans not fly a jet aircraft, even if his/her hands and arms do not reach the various controls and displays? We do not object to developing application software meant for critical operations, but adequate importance needs to be paid to factors like scheme of colors, types and sizes of fonts being used, meaningful graphics, and most importantly the target consumer.

In our country, we face incompatibility with products designed for everyday use in our daily lives. Regardless of the definition of design, it is widely understood that all designed creations are intended for human use and should aim to satisfy and engage all the five senses. To ensure the success of any design, it must not only cater to the physical and mental aspects of its users but also extend beyond addressing their needs and desires. (Karwowski et al., 2011; Norman, 2007; Strasser, 2022)

My personal experience as a consultant in the industry has been less than encouraging. The concept of human-centered design for machines, workplaces, workstations, and working conditions is lacking in many places. Recently, some industries have begun initiatives to humanize workstations and improve ergonomics in work practices. However, these efforts represent only a drop in the ocean of problems that exist.

The question is, with the present rush of developing designers how far we will be able to address the basic design issues in India? As per some statistics, there are 2,000+ Design Colleges in India. Out of these colleges, 1,100+ Design schools in India are privately owned, 300+ colleges are owned by the government, and 120+ colleges are owned by semi-government organizations. (<https://www.shiksha.com/design/colleges/colleges-india>, 2024) Thousands of students are graduating every year with a degree in design in hand. Last few years, as an academician I have had the opportunity to interact with a large number of UG students from a few design colleges/universities and I have heard an equivocal statement from most of them: "Trust me, the design landscape in India is evolving rapidly, but whether it's heading in the right direction is still up for debate. As a product design student for the past four years, I've learned new processes and skills, yet I remain uncertain about my future as an industrial designer".

Many of the students believe that many designers are shifting their careers to interaction design rather than exploring other areas; this shift is diverting attention from essential design fields and this needs a solution. Creating pretty UIs, branding, or rendering in software like Key Shot is important, but it seems we are crowding an already saturated area. Many designers are competing in these spaces rather than addressing fundamental issues. This overemphasis on aesthetics and trendy fields is overshadowing the need for practical, problem-solving in design.

For instance, service and system design fields are often overlooked. Budding student designers are reluctant to explore these areas, which are crucial for creating comprehensive solutions. (Katzan, 2011; Sangiorgi, 2009) They believe that

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while the challenge of working on polished interfaces and sleek renders is appealing, it's at the cost of neglecting the core purpose of design: solving real-world problems.

Design is still not perceived as a tool for solving problems for everyone. Instead, designer products are often seen as luxuries rather than essentials. Everything must be well-thought-out and planned before manufacturing, ensuring that design is accessible and beneficial for all, especially in a developing country like India.

Ultimately, while the design industry in India is flourishing, we need to ensure that it is solving the right problems, creating meaningful solutions, and generating ergonomic products. (Sah et al., 2022; Yadav et al., 2023). The true measure of design's impact should be seen in the improvement of living standards, not just in the number of likes on Behance or connections on LinkedIn. Only then can we truly harness the power of design to improve lives and drive progress.

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